

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: EKI****FIRST NAME: GEORGE****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US XUK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian parenthetical/in-text references:

The author X did did not use Zotero to insert references.

The author X did did not use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Writing a good academic essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7–12)
2. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 33–39)
3. Style guide (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 40–42)
4. CMS crib sheet(Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 43–57)
5. Sample corrections to papers (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 65–71)

WRITING AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

It took me three years to decide whether to apply for a Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) program. My hesitancy came from the fact that I needed to be more confident that I would have the time and commitment to complete it. Finding a school and the right program was challenging when I finally applied. I finally started the Ph.D. in International Public Health in May 2023 but needed clarification. It is my first time doing an online school program which is a clear departure from the in-person programs I was used to. When I finally clicked and commenced the study program on the LMS portal, my fears disappeared, and I could finally confront my fears. Navigating the resource materials, such as the videos and tutorial guide, I realized that this would undoubtedly be different from a master's degree program. I like to research as my work as a social and behavior change specialist relies mainly on it to design, implement, and evaluate programs. But academic writing is very different from regular program research writing.

The ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack is ideal for any beginner in academic essay writing. It contains the must-know in academic writing, and the revision of the course pack was quite thorough. The course pack is a deliberate attempt to help new students,

particularly Ph.D. students, to have an excellent start to academic writing. At first reading, I was scared about how I would be able to know and apply most of the ideas, but when I reread it for the second time, things started to get more precise. The course pack outline allowed me to familiarize myself with new things I had not taken seriously, even during my master's degree program. The content of the course pack is well-sequenced, from how to write an academic essay to an example of what a typical response paper looks like. Worthy of note are the details of various topics covered by the course pack.

An example is the clarity given to the steps someone should take to organize an academic essay. I found it interesting to read about how someone could manage ideas in preparation for academic essay writing and some simple rules of thumb that someone could follow to achieve a good outcome with the essay writing. The pack also brought the need to choose a style for essay writing, which could be the American or British style. Each of these styles also follows some rules in spelling. The chapter on the use of punctuation was an eye-opener for me as this is one area I have always paid less attention to. It will help improve my writing as I progress with my studies.

I will focus on five significant concepts presented in the course pack in this response paper. The response paper will highlight learnings from the various materials, such as the tutorial videos and the course pack. These concepts include academic essay writing, plagiarism, style guide, CMS crib sheet, and paper sample corrections.

2) WRITING AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

The ACA-401/ACA401D first chapter of the course pack introduces academic essay writing. It defines academic essay writing as nonfictional writing produced as part of academic work (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7). Academic writing may or may not be published, and examples of such include research findings or empirical fieldwork reports. This chapter presents an easy-to-follow heading that captures what a student needs to know and do to write an academic essay. It begins with starting essay writing and research, organizing ideas, referencing, and handing in the paper. A scholarly article aims to communicate an argument using evidence.

Like every other endeavor, sound planning helps achieve a better essay writing outcome. I agree with the paper that an essay plan is critical and will help guide the research, as it will contain initial thoughts and ideas and the type of information needed for the essay writing. The chapter also emphasizes the need for an early start, as an essay would require time for researching the topic, gathering the materials, and eventually writing. Early preparation and a clearly defined plan are essential to writing a good essay.

Gathering materials for essay writing requires researching the topic and then organizing the ideas logically using the evidence obtained. One should make Notes when collecting essay materials (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 8). Notes that include information sources, bibliographies, authors' names, dates, titles, publishers, and places of publication would prove helpful in essay writing. Essay writing requires creative and critical thinking, and the essay should include evidence for and against the idea of the topic

while providing a superior argument for one's standpoint (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 9). This idea of having and examining differing views in an essay strikes a chord with me. In my previous academic writing, my emphasis has always been on evidence that supports my arguments—but having an opposing view and explaining why one idea is more superior or convincing than the other further shows how much effort was put into the research to reach that standpoint.

An academic essay usually has a structured format. The format provides a basis for organizing the paper. It helps organize all the ideas into a logical flow, making it easy to communicate the writer's views and easy for readers to understand. In EUCLID, the structure for academic essays should have an introduction, body, and conclusion (Laurent and Gulma 2021, 10).

The next step is to produce a draft after gathering ideas and information for a paper. This draft helps the writer create a refined version of the essay. The authors' suggestion of producing a draft paper which is then further reviewed, is in line with the idea of having a writing plan. An initial draft certainly will be a product of this plan. The essay is complete with references. Reference is a requirement for all academic papers (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 11). The references help to guide against plagiarism which is an academic offense. One needs to understand the referencing style to use for the essay. For EUCLID, the referencing style is Turabian style (author-date).

Before submitting the essay, one should read and follow the course guidelines. Submission of the paper is the last part of the essay writing task and would also require one to clearly understand the following: what date the assignment is due, where and to whom to submit it.

A guide on the choice and use of the English language in essay writing was provided. It is important to note that one must either use the American or English language version in writing. Sticking to a choice of English language version helps to avoid mistakes or errors that may arise from mixing both.

3) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism presented in the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack highlights a sensitive area in academic essay writing that I consider very significant that one should take seriously. It is a severe offense, and EUCLID also takes this very seriously. According to the EUCLID, plagiarism is a writer's use of information without crediting the author or source of information (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34). A journal of universal computer science described plagiarism as a "theft of intellectual property" (Maurer, Kappe, and Zaka 2006, 1050). These definitions clearly show the severity of plagiarism. One must credit the authors and mention the sources of information that a writer consulted.

There are different instances where one should give credit to authors, including when using paraphrases, quotes, statistical/ data, or visuals. Failure to give credit is an

offense and can have consequences for the writer. It is also essential that one cites authors' work and sources correctly.

The chapter provided clear guidance on citation and two ways to do it, i.e., in-text citation and list of work cited. It also mainly gave attention to issues of quotation and paraphrasing with examples. The examples were beneficial in providing clarity to the explanations. I found the in-text citation approach consistent with the EUCLID Turabian referencing style (author's name, date, and page number).

Furthermore, it provided tips on the use of quotations and paraphrasing. These tips help to ensure that the context and original meanings of statements from original authors are not lost. However, one should limit the use of quotations as it has the potential to make one's work look less original. While for paraphrasing, the writer must ensure that the words used must not resemble that of the original author either in language or style and must also be careful not to misrepresent the author's statement (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 36).

Lastly, the chapter also mentioned when not to cite in academic writing. The authors opined that citing all things is impossible and that one way to know about common information is when the information is found in many sources. Interestingly, it, however, provided a format for the listing of citations or references. This information was interesting reading for me as I had always had challenges referencing books and online works.

4) STYLE GUIDE

As clearly outlined in the course pack, this concept is one of the critical areas students should pay attention to. As a Ph.D. student, this is particularly useful as it defines the writing style acceptable and recommended by EUCLID. The Chicago Rules (Turabian) is the recommended style by EUCLID, though it also recognizes other international rules.

According to the authors, a style guide is a writer's way of documenting an approach to certain elements of a writing style that should be consistent (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 41). A writer's use of a style guide helps ensure coherence and consistency. EUCLID recommends using American English even though the British versions are still acceptable. Before now, I have always needed help with consistency in using styles. I had not given attention to styles, but now I can see that if I am to achieve consistency in my writing, I need to stick to a particular style, preferably the American one, as EUCLID recommended.

It was interesting reading to see that different writings, such as technical, business, and journalism, all follow the style guide that keeps their writing consistent, and an example is the British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) style guide. This guide indeed points to the fact that a style guide is invaluable for any writer.

To make writing much easier for students, particularly Ph.D. students, EUCLID provided a template that is downloadable and ready to use by students. The template is like a 'hit the ground running' tool for students like me. The template is well structured, taking away the burden of structuring the pages and headings. The choice of font sizes was

explicitly explained and inputted into the template and thus saving students time which ordinarily would have been wasted trying to clarify many of these issues from the supervisors. It also guides the students in terms of the length of the response paper, thus helping to ensure that the paper is short and brief.

5) **CHICAGO MANUAL OF STYLE CRIB SHEET**

This chapter of the ACA-401/ACA-401D centers on using the Chicago style, understanding the specifications, and some clear examples. The Chicago style, also referred to as the Turabian style, is the style of formatting books, research papers, term papers, Thesis and Dissertations in the Chicago and the Turabian manuals (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 44).

The Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) Crib sheet contains detailed topics to guide a writer to use the style effectively. The areas it covers will help a writer achieve consistency. In the areas of spelling, it recommends the use of Webster's Third New International Dictionary and Merriam-Webster's Collegiate Dictionary. While in the use of abbreviations such as e.g., etc., and i.e., it recommends that one should use in parenthetical comments injected into text and, when not in parentheses, spelled out in full. I found this interesting, as I have always used these abbreviations in writing without observing these rules.

Capitalization in the Chicago style uses full caps, heading caps, and sentence caps. It was interesting to see that full caps capitalize every word's character used in major headings. I have always mixed the caps with smaller letters, even when I use them for headings. The heading caps capitalize the first and last words and all pronouns, nouns, adjectives, and conjunctions. In contrast, the sentence caps capitalize the first word of a title or heading (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 46).

Compound words are two or more words that work together in a particular other. The order cannot be rearranged or reversed without changing the meaning. To get this right, the author suggests the use of a dictionary. The chapter provides a clear explanation for using compound words using hyphens and when not using hyphens. It was interesting to understand that compound words, whether nouns or adjectives, are hyphenated in a sentence. While conditional compounds are hyphenated when used as adjectives. It also provides a guide to the use of hyphens with Prefixes. Most prefixes do not need hyphens, but there could be exceptions to this rule. But as a rule, it is always advised to consult a dictionary to get it right.

The use of italics and quotation marks came as new learning to me. The rules for its use have always been confusing for me, but the authors made this clear. Italics and quotation marks are both used to highlight, note, and translate words in a sentence. It goes ahead to provide a guide on its use. One should avoid its overuse as it could make them lose their essence. For italics, one should add them to a word or phrase only when used for the first time, and after that, one should use plain text. As a rule, the quotation must be placed in quotation marks or indented as a block quote and citation, note, or parenthetical citation where readers are linked to the source document (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021,

48). There are some permissions to changes in the use of quotations, such as when quoting in a foreign language, when the quote is from another citation, adding emphasis to words, or when adding materials to a quote. When one uses terms or concepts in a quote, it is vital to indicate that the original has been quoted correctly using the Latin word *sic*. Despite the rule of ensuring that one captures direct quotes precisely, there are some instances where changes are permitted. Some of these instances include the change of double quotes to single quotes, insertion of notes and references in a quote, change of capitalized words to lowercase, and where there are typographic errors.

In terms of page formatting, the Chicago-style page format clearly explained this course pack. While CMS focuses on book publishing, it provides little information in formatting papers. The Turabian manual for writers' guides formats for papers, theses, and dissertations. The Chicago page format is clearly explained and provides a guide to areas such as margin, indent, paper, alignment, font, and page numbers. The recommended page dimension is 8½ by 11 inches with a 1-inch margin across the four edges of the paper. Times Roman with a twelve-point type is recommended. The indent is one-half inch with double spacing, while the page number is to be placed at the bottom middle of the paper (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 50)

Other parts of the Chicago style include footnotes, headings, listings, tables, and references. The Chicago style provides the proper guidance on how to do this right. This guidance will serve as student reference material when writing a paper. I consulted the materials during my writing of this response paper. Of important note is that the Chicago-style writing materials serve as reminders to writers. They may be lengthy or hard to remember; the rule of thumb here is always to be guided by it when writing to ensure consistency.

6) SAMPLE CORRECTIONS TO PAPERS

The sample correction paper was one of my favorite parts of the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack. The earlier part of the pack describes what it contains and how one can use it. But the sample correction paper was the icing on the cake for me. It brought all the issues discussed onto paper. It gave me a clear example of all that I have been reading in the previous pages of the course pack.

The sample paper was like an introduction to the EUCLID template for response papers. It clearly explained what I needed to do when writing my response papers. I agree with the authors for adding this sample paper as it is the best example of what the pack discussed. Starting from the top of the template, it provides spaces to enter the last name of the student, the course name, and the page number. This identification makes it easier for the supervisor to identify the student and the course name.

Beneath the heading are the students' specific details, including student names, course names, student country, course code, program code, paper number, and the supervisor's name. This part gives detailed information about the writer. This information makes it easy for me to know what paper I am working on or have worked on.

The information on the author's use of grammar, writing style, references, Zotero, and Grammarly is a reminder for me to ensure that I follow the rules. One can forget or miss out on some of the writing rules for EUCLID, but this section serves as a checklist of the must-do in writing.

The main body of the sample paper brought to the fore a particular writing approach and showed where the errors were in the paper. The comments by the supervisor in the sample paper were for a student to avoid repeating similar mistakes. The writer in the sample paper had errors that the supervisor pointed out. An example is using the word 'I learned' by the sample paper writer. Since the response paper was for a student to engage with the paper, it also provided a guide on particular words to avoid, one of which is 'I learned.' The writer of the sample paper demonstrated simplicity in his engagement with the course pack as well as was able to follow the writing style as recommended. This example made it easier for me to follow through with my thoughts and express them as simply as possible with consistency. This sample paper showed me some dos and don'ts that apply in paper writing, and it was instrumental and handy in supporting me in coming up with my response paper.

Intext citation recommendation by EUCLID was followed by the sample writer, and with that, I was eventually able to install Zotero referencing software and Grammarly. Using the Turabian style, these two packages were beneficial for grammar, tenses, punctuation, and citation.

The comments by the supervisor came in very handy during my writing. I noted the supervisor's corrections and ensured I did not make similar mistakes in my paper.

7) CONCLUSION

Reading through the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack was highly valuable for me as a Ph.D. student also offering the program as an online course. The course pack is an excellent introduction to paper writing, as I will write many papers during the program. This introductory pack sets a foundation for me to build on as I realize I will still consult with it as I proceed in my program.

There was no better way to launch me into the Ph.D. program than this course pack. It has awakened and renewed my vigor for writing, but this time with clear guidance stipulated by EUCLID. The materials provided, such as the short instructional videos on the school's website, enriched it despite the challenges of kickstarting a learning program after years of completing a master's program.

This course pack also made me realize the work, commitment, and dedication required to see through the program. It has also opened my eyes to many things in writing that I usually see in publications but have yet to learn what they mean. I am delighted to pursue this program because these new ways of writing papers will continue for some years and help me achieve some level of expertise and consistency, especially in publications.

The course pack is a 'must have' material that I will hold on to as I proceed in my Ph.D. pursuit, and I am definite that I will constantly use it to improve my writing.

REFERENCES

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